

EVIDENCE OF CARBOXY ESTER MECHANISMS
IN NITRIFICATION FROM THE DYNAMIC
REACTION KINETICS AT NATURAL
CONCENTRATIONS.

Part II. Evidence for the Involvement of a Carboxy
Phosphate Ester in the Oxidation of Ammonia where
Zero Order, First Order, Half Order and Auto Catalytic
Kinetics can be Observed Depending on the
Experimental Methodology but Michaelis-Menten
Kinetics is Not Supported.

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Abstract

The kinetics of nitrification has been investigated using a mixing tank and a submerged horizontal biofilter in fast recycle acting as a batch reactor. It was inoculated with pure cultures of *Nitrosomonas europaea* and *Nitrobacter europaea*. The system was maintained at a steady-state on Skinner and Walker medium, lacking organic carbon substrates, at a pH of 8.0 and a temperature of 24°C. Ammonia concentrations were held at those corresponding to aquaculture recycle systems and natural water courses. A constant high liquid velocity through the biofilter was maintained to minimise liquid film mass transfer diffusion resistance. Preliminary pulse tests were conducted that determined the reaction kinetics to follow zero order, half order but not Michaelis-Menten kinetics. Depending upon the experimental setting auto catalytic kinetics were also observed. There is thus evidence for the use of an activator in ammonia oxidation. Nitrite levels were extremely low indicating that the nitrite oxidation reaction is faster than ammonia oxidation. Bicarbonate ions and phosphate ions are removed at higher rates than would be expected from growth. Without buffering the pH of the system fell to 4.0. The results are compatible with the oxidation of ammonia occurring via a hypothesised carboxylic route to nitrite.

Key words: Nitrification, Pulse testing, Carbamate, Reaction kinetics, Auto catalytic

1. Introduction

In a previous article [1] the reaction kinetics of ammonia oxidation to nitrite was examined in a dynamic aquaculture recycle system using chi-square probability fits. The data gave insights into the dynamic behaviour of the bacteria outwith the constraints of growth studies or high substrate concentration environments. Two possibilities arose. Firstly that the active film area was around half of the available area, although visual inspection of the biofilm did not support this. The second possibility is that the observed diffusion coefficient is around half of that of ammonia in pure water. In addition there was also reason to believe that the reaction mechanisms involve the use of an activator. With the introduction of a liquid film mass transfer correction factor various kinetic reaction equations were successfully tested. Zero order is not compatible with the observed liquid film diffusion. First order, half order, Michaelis-Menten and sigmoidal kinetics were accepted. Surprisingly second order kinetics was also accepted.

In summary the above conclusions warrant an examination of how nitrification might then proceed. The current proposed mechanisms involve toxic substrates and intermediates. In general the non-ionic forms of the substrates are toxic and thus pH influences the toxicity as shown in Fig. 1 for 1 mg/l TAN and 10 mg/l TAN.

Figure 1: Substrate and "Intermediate" Concentrations

Hydroxylamine as an intermediate introduces very large problems as it is a

mutagen. This is not a process that one would like to use in mass production and in particular given the close proximity to operators and the public (other proteins and enzymes). From a chemical engineering perspective, if one is being presented with a laboratory scale reaction to be scaled up which has very serious toxicity, corrosion or safety issues associated with it, then one goes back to the chemist to discuss alternative reaction pathways.

Hydrazine, yet another toxic substrate, stops nitrite formation. Indeed it was once used as an oxygen scavenger in cooling water systems, in which N_2 is formed. Hydrazine was also added to water as an iron passivator preventing corrosion. It is plausible that it reacts with the monooxygenase enzyme, but less so a hydrolysis enzyme. The priority for hydroxylamine being an intermediate is that hydrazine binds to the hydrolysis enzyme, but not the mono oxygenase enzyme. What is not being accounted for is the possibility that the actual "intermediate" is broken down to hydroxylamine upon the presence of hydrazine. In addition there is a problem with hydroxylamine as an intermediate in that none of the subsequent proposed intermediates have been found without it.

It can be theorised that rather than involving intermediates yet to be detected during normal ammonia oxidation, a different reaction route is used in which additional reactants are involved that are so prevalent as to be overlooked. The two reactants that come to mind are water and carbon dioxide, in the form of bicarbonate ions. Before the advent of methyl, dimethyl, and trimethylamine carbon dioxide was removed from process gases with ammonia solutions. The following equilibria are established [2][3]

The second equilibrium shows the formation of carbamate (of ammonia) NH_2COO^- , or also called carbamic acid. The equilibrium data for the formation of carbamate and the resulting Gibbs free energy indicates that the equilibrium has no overwhelming tendency to shift to the left or right. The amount of energy involved is not large, but its formation occurs at high concentrations of ammonia and bicarbonate ions. The earlier use of these reactions in the process industries involved high concentrations at high pressures and much of the data is for these conditions with the exception of where water is being treated to remove ammonia[4]. Under the conditions found in natural watercourses the amounts of carbamate are lower than those of ammonia by a factor of one thousand as shown in Fig. 2. This in turn suggests that ammonia and a bicarbonate ion would have to preferentially undergo a reaction to form carbamate either at or near the enzyme or alternatively a carrier that performs this task is involved.

Although liquid film diffusion involvement is what the kinetic data from the smolt hatchery is showing, it is also suspected that the bacteria were altering the reaction rate too. An activator would fit this scenario. The oxidation of carbamate, like that of ammonia, would require energy to overcome the thermo-

Figure 2: Carbamate Concentrations

dynamic barrier involved. The use of an activator would thus be beneficial both in making carbamate and oxidising it, provided the majority of the energy can be recovered. On the grounds of efficiency one would expect the bacteria to use an energy source which was not excessively higher than the energy required for reaction. The amount of energy transferred by ATP upon reaction is about 30 kJ/mol and for NADH about 220 kJ/mol. The most likely source of chemical energy to overcome the thermodynamic barrier (around 17 kJ/mol) for the oxidation of ammonia is thus ATP. The overall reaction to make carbamate would involve ammonia gas, a bicarbonate ion and an ATP molecule. To check if such a reaction had already been found in biology, a biological pathway chart was consulted. The formation of carbamate of ammonia by enzymes is not only possible, but is already known to occur. On the urea cycle, an enzyme-catalyzed reaction involving ammonia gas, bicarbonate ion and ATP is observed. The reaction forms carbamate phosphate, a key intermediate in the formation of pyrimidines, arginine, and urea. A well-understood enzyme that performs this reaction is carbamyl phosphate synthetase obtained from *Escherichia coli*. The substrate to this reaction is either ammonia gas or glutamine.

The reaction scheme as given by Holden [5] is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Scheme of the reaction catalysed by carbamoyl phosphate synthetase

Another bacterial enzyme called carbamate kinase also forms carbamate phosphate, but this is reversible and favours ATP synthesis. It is not suggested that ammonia oxidising bacteria enzymes are closely related, rather that the carbamate reaction pathway is feasible from a biochemistry perspective.

The main research objective remained to investigate the nitrification reaction kinetics further and to this aim an experimental rig was designed. The experimental philosophy was to conduct experiments analogous to pulse testing as conducted in the process industries. That is to add a substrate over a short period of time and then to investigate the response. The method has the advantage that no significant change in the numbers of bacteria can be expected if the experiment is carefully designed to produce a response while remaining within the operating limits of the normal process. This paper examines data from the initial experiments conducted to determine how big the changes should be and the general behaviour of the process. This could be equated to preliminary pulse/step testing as conducted in the process industries prior to the main tests.

The four types of apparent reaction kinetics given in Table. 1 will be examined using their integrated forms.

Kinetics	Equation	Integrated Equation
Zero Order	$r = k_I\omega$	$C_{in} - C = k_I\omega t$
Half Order	$r = k_I\omega C^{0.5}$	$\sqrt{C_{in}} - \sqrt{C} = 1/2k_I\omega t$
First Order	$r = k_I\omega C$	$\ln\left(\frac{C_{in}}{C}\right) = k_I\omega t$
Michaelis-Menten	$r = \frac{k_I\omega C}{1 + k_{II}C}$	$\frac{1}{(C_{in} - C)} \ln\left(\frac{C_{in}}{C}\right) = k_I\omega \frac{t}{(C_{in} - C)} - k_{II}$

Table 1: Rate Equations Tested

2. Experimental

2.1. Experimental Rig

To conduct the studies a pilot plant scale recycle reactor rig was built. The concept follows that often used to investigate solid chemical catalysts with fluid reactants. By maintaining a high degree of recycle the system behaves as a batch reactor in which the substrate concentrations can simply be plotted against time after the addition of the reactant. The mixing tank was 29 cm in diameter with a height of 29 cm to the overflow. The tank and the piping gave a liquid volume of 24 liters. Two horizontal submerged filters, each made from grey PVC piping of an internal diameter of 155 mm and a length of 102 cm, were constructed. Distributor plates were used at the filter ends rather than larger packing. The filter medium was crushed rock (granite-based), which was sieved to remove fines. The projected Feret's diameter of the rock was measured as 6 mm. The small size offers a large area and eliminates wall voidage effects, but has the potential for blockages to occur. It was planned to rotate the filters in such a case to backwash them, but this was never required. The filter liquid volume was 7 l giving a total system volume of 31 l. The superficial flow velocity was chosen to correspond to the maximum used in the aquaculture recycle system, with the reduced particle diameter a Reynolds number of around 194 was achieved. Mixing studies were carried out on the experimental rig prior to the kinetic experiments, that confirmed ideal mixing in the tank and near plug flow behaviour through the filters at the recycle rates used. From a dynamic simulation of the system, in which the filter was modelled as 80 tanks in series, it was expected that the concentrations in and out of the filter would be very close after two recycle loops with no transients thereafter. Samples were thus taken several minutes after any substrate addition corresponding to over 3 recycle loops for the first preliminary pulse test.

As the experimental design did not involve smolts and feeding cycles it eliminated questions regarding the influence of BOD on nitrification, but it also

Mineral Nutrient	g/l
$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	0.235
KH_2PO_4	0.2
$\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.04
$\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.04
FeSO_4	0.5 mg not analytical grade

Table 2: Medium composition

removed the dynamics of an aquaculture system.

Figure 4: Experimental Rig

2.2. Start-up

To seed the nitrifying filters, pure cultures of *Nitrosomonas europaea* and *Nitrobacter europaea* were grown in 500 ml of a Skinner and Walker's type medium [6] given in Table 2 in 2 litre glass flasks, covered with aluminium foil, under aseptic conditions. For the *Nitrobacter* 50 mg of NaNO_2 replaced the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$.

The size of the rig meant that sterilized operation would have been difficult and the research aim was to yield information relevant to operating recycle aquaculture systems. The rig was first recirculated with distilled water. The nutrients were then added to give the same strength in the rig water as in the growth medium prior to inoculation with the flocculant bacteria. As the

medium lacks a carbon source, it was assumed that this kept non-nitrifiers to a very low level. It was also assumed that the population of nitrifiers remained predominantly of the species added. The filter, standing upright, was filled with deionised water and the block valves closed. Like the filters in the recycle aquaculture system they were mounted horizontally with a threaded bolt to bleed air if required.

To build and maintain the bacterial population at a constant level, the metering pumps supplied nutrients and buffer at a constant rate. Evaporation losses were compensated for with deionized water. Solutions of Skinner and Walker, without the NaEDTA and phenol red, and 5 wt/vol Na_2CO_3 solutions were large enough for several days of continuous operation.

The introduced nitrifying bacteria were in floc form and for the first two weeks no buffering was required. The mixing tank lid was then covered with aluminium foil to stop light entering. Thereafter there was noticeable bacterial growth and a need to buffer the rig. To test if the light entering the mixing tank might be responsible for the inhibition of the initially flocculant bacteria, the foil was removed. After cleaning the biofilm from the tank walls, no subsequent growth of a biofilm in the mixing tank was noticed. The start-up issue thus may have been due to light disrupting nitrification [7] [8] [9] and possibly biofilm adhesion.

2.3. Establishing Steady State Conditions and Refinements

Mixing studies conducted before the experiments confirmed the experimental mixed flow assumption and that a mixer originally envisaged was not required. Likewise an aerator was found not to be needed as the returning water aerated the water enough. It was also established that the temperature in the mixing tank was constant in the laboratory conditions. With the use of a portable cooler the experimental rig was run at temperatures between 5 and 22°C at pH 8.0. However, at no time was the biomass killed or the filter blocked, avoiding the necessity of a restart. The second back-up filter in the design was thus never used. The experimental rig was run for over 8 weeks at which point it was decided that a steady-state condition had been reached.

For the experiments a flowrate of 20.4 l/min through the filter was run with 0.27 kg/h of the above Skinner and Walker solution being dosed. The dilute sodium carbonate solution dosing was set to give a pH of 8.0. The water temperature was 24°C with the dissolved oxygen concentration measured to be above 8 ppm at all times.

2.4. Analytics

In the preliminary pulse test the concentration of ammonia was much higher than those in the recycle aquaculture systems. In order to determine concentrations outside the linear range of the test, the samples were diluted with ultra pure water. The lowest dilution within the linear range was used for analyzing the reaction rate. The ammonia determination was performed using an alkaline citrate medium with sodium hypochlorite and phenol [10]. During colour development the flasks were kept away from light. The number of samples and the

time constraints regarding colour development required the use of automatic pipettes. In the case of an outlier, the next higher dilution value was used. The experimental error involved in the ammonia analysis for the samples was around 5 %, but for highly diluted samples (above 10 fold dilution i.e. 1 mg/l $\text{NH}_3 - \text{N}$ and all the $\text{NO}_3^- - \text{N}$ samples) the errors involved might have been somewhat higher. The other water analysis were conducted as described in the same reference. The methods were routinely used by the aquaculture research group.

2.5. Preliminary Pulse Testing Experiments

The amount of substrate to be used was weighed, and the volumetric flowrate was read from the rotameter. The metering pump was then switched off and the pH controller switched on. A peristaltic pump delivered dilute sodium carbonate during ammonia oxidation. A quantity of water was then taken from the sampling point after the rotameter, and the substrate was dissolved in it. The water was then returned to the rig and left for 5 minutes to ensure that the substrate had been mixed and that the concentration was uniform throughout the system. The required fluid volume for analysis was measured and placed in its labelled polyethylene container for freezing. Temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, conductivity and phenolphthalein alkalinity, total alkalinity, carbonate alkalinity and total CO_2 were also measured. The frozen samples were then later analysed for ammonia, nitrite and nitrate. Although the amounts removed were planned in advance to limit the water removed, if the experiment did take longer the number of analysis were reduced. For the preliminary pulse test samples were taken before and after the filter to confirm the low conversion across the filter and represents a further check in addition to the tracer checks. The differences between the inlet and outlet concentrations were more a result of the order and time involved in taking each sample. A mean value is thus also valid.

3. Results

3.1. Preliminary Pulse Testing Experiments

The series of experiments detailed here were conducted to obtain basic information on how the bacteria respond to changes in substrate concentration. The first experiment was conducted to find out just how much substrate to add so that the bacteria exhibited a large (control) response. An impulse addition of ammonia 7.15 mg/l $\text{NH}_3 - \text{N}$ was made (a concentration well outside those found in aquaculture) and samples were taken over a time of more than 13 hours. The experiment was maintained at a pH of 8.0 by adding sodium carbonate, the same pH as that maintained for growing the bacteria. The pH ensures very low CO_2 levels. The mixing tank dissolved oxygen concentration never fell below 7.5 mg/l.

Figure 5 illustrate the ammonia and nitrite response along with the conductivity and alkalinity response.

Figure 5: Substrate and Ionic Concentrations

Figure 6: Initial Kinetics and New Phase Kinetics

Figure 7: Repeat Experiment

Fitting Michaelis-Menten/Monod/saturation kinetics to all the data does not yield very good fits. On closer inspection there is a change in the kinetics at around 9 hours. The changes around this time are real and not the result of experimental uncertainties, the bacteria are seen to be switching to another operating mode or phase. Excellent fits are obtained for zero order kinetics in the first 9 hours, corresponding to a TAN down to 2 mg/l. Taking the initial concentration for a new phase to be at 641 minutes and averaging the inlet and outlet concentrations, integrated reaction kinetic plots can be made as in Fig. 6. Very good fits are obtained for half order and first order kinetics. Half order kinetics, based upon the correlation coefficients, is judged to fit marginally better than first order kinetics. Michaelis-Menten kinetics is by comparison not well fitted. The fitted apparent constants and the correlation ratios are given in Table. 3.

Despite the large ammonia addition the nitrite concentration was only $64\mu\text{g/l NO}_2^-$ N, falling below $5\mu\text{g/l - N}$ after two hours. This indicates that the nitrite reaction is much faster than the ammonia reaction. It is thus implied that nitrite spikes occur as a result of growth rate imbalances from large sustained changes rather than from short lived disturbances. As expected, the nitrate concentration rose during the experiment.

The total alkalinity was only measured for the first 9 hours due to sample volume constraints. The water conductivity however was measured for the whole period. A drop in conductivity and the titrated alkalinity in the first 9 hours is

Pre-Pulse Testing Data at Re 194		
Kinetics	R^2	$k_I\omega$
Zero	0.999	0.576
Half	0.995	0.007
First	0.985	0.0073
Michaelis-Menten	0.103	-

Table 3: Apparent Kinetic Constant

observed, despite the sodium carbonate addition maintaining the pH. The water conductivity however continues to drop thereafter and by significant amounts.

3.2. Pulse Testing Reproducibility Experiments

The next experiment was conducted to check that the pulse reaction studies could be reproduced. Two pulse experiments were performed under the same experimental conditions, with the TAN under 1 mg/l, at an interval of 24 hours. The usual substrate dosing was maintained between the experiments. The bacteria can thus not be described as resting or in a starving state. After allowing a few minutes for the substrate to mix thoroughly with the rig water, samples were taken over the next 80 minutes. The sampling interval was reduced for the second run following the rapid fall in the ammonia in the first. The graph of total ammonia concentration versus time for both experiments is shown in Fig. 7.

The differences between the two curves is very pronounced and represent totally different reaction kinetics for the same experiment. It might be thought that the number of bacteria was higher in the first experiment. However, a change in the number of bacteria would be expected to alter the slope of the reaction curve, but not its shape.

3.3. No Buffering

During these preliminary experiments a further experiment was conducted. Ammonium sulphate was added with the metering pump and the peristaltic pump adding buffer switched off. The system was thus not buffered, other than by carbon dioxide in the air for several days. The pH fell from pH 8.0, as would be expected, to 4.01 ± 0.01 , but it did not fall any lower. It should be stressed that this experiment does not indicate that growth is possible at this pH, but rather that ammonia oxidation stopped.

4. Discussion

4.1. Preliminary Pulse Testing Experiments

During the first 9 hours the bacteria are operating at a maximum rate, presumably controlling the ammonia oxidation reactions at this rate. Oxidising 1

mg TAN requires 4.57 mg of oxygen [11] and although the mixing tank dissolved oxygen never fell below 7.6 mg/l it could have been limiting the reactions, if at all, at a local level for a very short time at the highest concentrations. There is no obvious product inhibition behaviour that might be expected if toxic hydroxylamine was made in significant quantities. As the reaction rate is constant in this period so too should be the rate of energy generation.

Prehn's [12] conducted experiments in a fast recycle batch reactor setting with nitrifying filter elements taken from a recycle aquaculture system. They first did experiments from 1 mg/l TAN down to 0.35 mg/l TAN which took 100-300 minutes depending on the superficial velocity (2.5-40 m/h). After a 5 hour break they then repeated the experiments, but with a TAN from 3 mg/l to 1.5 mg/l. The pre-pulse testing here involved a higher starting concentration at the higher superficial velocity of 64 m/h without any interruption, although the bacteria themselves paused somewhat around a concentration of 2 mg/l TAN. While the experimental details are different, the results here as given in Table. 3 are similar to the $0.0107 k_1 \omega$ for first order kinetics found by Prehn. A reduction of the TAN from 3 mg/l to 1.5 mg/l took around 156 min compared to 170-180 min in Prehn's experiment. The reduction from 1 mg/l TAN to 0.35 mg/l TAN took 90 minutes here, at a higher superficial velocity amongst other factors, which compared to 100-300 minutes in Prehn's data. The experimental area to system volume used here was much larger than in Prehn's work (380 to $80.6 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$) and it is anticipated that the active area was correspondingly smaller and thus not limited by area. The biofilm thickness likewise is expected to be correspondingly low.

Sodium carbonate solution was dosed to successfully maintain the pH, nevertheless the titrated alkalinity is seen to drop. The nitrate concentration climbs to a value consistent with the nitrite being oxidized fully to nitrate. The nitrate concentrations were comparable to recycle aquaculture systems. Unfortunately the nitrate was not measured after 9 hours, but it is not thought that denitrification took place as oxygen limitation should no longer be a limitation. The experimental rig water does not correspond to fresh water nor sea water as it contains significant amounts of phosphates in the growth medium. The titrated alkalinity is thus a function of the phosphate ions as well as carbonate ions [13]. Ammonia gas also contributes to alkalinity, but at the pH of 8.0 it is not present in amounts so as to play a significant role.

The balanced equation from the known reaction stoichiometry with sodium carbonate is:

The United States Environmental Protection Agency [11] indicates that five carbons are used for every nitrogen (i.e. nitrifying bacteria have the stoichiometry $\text{C}_5\text{H}_7\text{NO}_2$) by growing bacteria. There is a wide range of yield coefficients in the literature with those of Skinner and Walker determined for *Nitrosomonas* sp. in their medium as 0.056 at 29°C and at a pH of 8.0. The yield coefficient

for *Nitrobacter* sp. is lower from 0.02 to at most 0.07 [14]. The loss of alkalinity is also given as between 6.0 and 7.4 mg [11]. The amount of sodium carbonate dosed in the experiment was at the upper range of the literature values. It is seen as probable that an amount of the bicarbonate ions removed were not used to form new cells.

The Aquion hydrochemistry software package (www.aqion.de/, Version 7.3.3), which uses PhreeqC [15] as its internal numerical solver, was used to test the scenarios. Such software enforces all the ionic balances and indicates when there is no solution possible. With nitrate not being removed the drop in conductivity can only be explained by the removal of phosphate ions. So as the TAN drops and the reaction rate switches to half order kinetics more phosphates are being removed from the water. They were most likely removed earlier, but not in the same amounts. The removal of phosphates would suggest that molecules containing phosphates, such as ADP, ATP and NADP, are being produced as the TAN decreases with the dissolved oxygen not limiting the reaction. With the TAN dropping the reaction rate is expected to decrease. An explanation for the production of ATP for example would be that it is being used to maintain the reaction rate and the energy production. Given that ammonia oxidation yields so little energy this energy would best be recovered in some way. The preliminary pulse testing experimental results thus supports the carbamate reaction pathway theory, which consumes bicarbonate ions and /or the retention of bicarbonate ions in enzymatic forms.

4.2. Pulse Testing Reproducibility Experiments

The response from the first experiment clearly was outside the normal process conditions and bacterial growth cannot be discounted. It also yields little information about any dynamics in the reaction kinetics. Thus the subsequent set of experiments was conducted at concentrations below 1 mg/l $\text{NH}_3 - \text{N}$, which also corresponds more to the concentrations found in recycle aquaculture systems and natural water courses. The repeat experiments illustrates the challenges of repeating biological experiments. The particular result shown in Fig. 7 appears to be connected with the experiment conducted prior to it. The first of the reproducibility experiments was conducted two days after the first experiment. This experiment lasted for over 13 hours and added significantly more ammonia (426 mg N) than the metering pump would have done over the same time interval (189 mg N). The bacteria initially reacted very slowly to the pulse. Within a short period of time the reaction rate is increased in an auto-catalytic way. The experiment is thus evidence for the use of an activator to alter the reaction rate in the reaction mechanisms. The amount of energy from ammonia oxidation is very limited and the electrons generated are needed for the peroxide formation. Their use is thus seen as an unlikely response to a low level substrate increase in which the energy to be gained is not significant. Wilhelm et al [16] have demonstrated that *Nitrosomonas europaea* "has the ability to instantly respond to ammonia" even after very prolonged starvation. It is thus very likely that low energy activators are used and these are capable of very rapidly increasing the reaction rate. In the second repeat experiment

this accelerated reaction rate is not apparent, the activator was in sufficient quantities so that no lag is observed.

Ammonia oxidation results in hydrogen ion production. Given that the bacteria grow on such low energy substrates, the use of the resulting proton gradient is probably a must from the point of view of control and optimization. It is likely that any ATP produced by a proton force is independent of the electron transport mechanisms. Given a pulse of substrate the bacteria could generate ATP and or higher energy molecules from the electrons. Upgrading ATP to a higher energy molecule is also possible, but this process is not 100% efficient. It would thus be expected that ATP is the molecule of choice for short to medium term biochemical processes. What is being suggested is that ATP is used as an activator to boost the reaction rate, that is otherwise cyclic in nature when at steady state. In the reverse case ATP could be generated by reducing the number of active sites. The electron chain forming the peroxide and its role in respiration does not have to be directly involved.

4.3. No Buffering

The third experiment is further evidence for the involvement of bicarbonate ions in ammonia oxidation. The cessation of ammonia oxidation at a pH of 4.01 corresponds exactly to the lower pH-limit at which bicarbonate ions exist in solution. An alternative but improbable explanation is that this is a coincidence and that some unknown mechanism also shares this lower pH limit. The traditional path of ammonia being oxidised to hydroxylamine gives no explanations for this observed lower pH limit. Traditional mechanism are given for ammonia gas and ammonia ion with the pH at the enzyme site being unknown.

4.4. Diffusion of Ammonia

In the previous article [1], in which the kinetics were determined to be subject to liquid film diffusion limitations, the diffusion coefficient value for ammonia in pure water was used as done by other authors. This is an oversimplification as the ammonia at the pH examined is mostly in its ionic form and bicarbonate ions are buffering the reaction. The movement of the ammonia ion thus depends upon the other ions present [17]. With bicarbonate ions acting more as a reactant, an ionic salt approach would be more appropriate. For a dilute solution of a single salt, such as ammonia/anion, the Nernst-Haskell equation can be used. From limiting ionic conductances in water at 25°C as used by PhreeqC [15] and using the Nernst-Haskell equation with the temperature correction recommended by Reid [18], the diffusion coefficient for various salt solutions are given in Table 4:

The diffusion coefficient for the ammonium/bicarbonate salt solution is half that for ammonia in water. The halving of the diffusion coefficient reduces the liquid film mass transfer coefficient by two thirds. This value would then explain to a significant degree the requirement of a mass transfer correction factor in the previous paper. With liquid film diffusion strongly controlling the reactions at low concentrations, then lower temperatures decrease the diffusion

Cation	Anion	25°C	15°C	12°C
NH_4^+	OH^-	2.88	2.18	1.99
NH_4^+	HCO_3^-	1.48	1.12	1.02
NH_4^+	$\frac{1}{2}\text{CO}_3^{2-}$	1.94	1.47	1.34
NH_4^+	$\frac{1}{3}\text{PO}_4^{3-}$	1.90	1.44	1.32
NH_4^+	NO_2^-	1.94	1.47	1.34
NH_4^+	NO_3^-	1.94	1.47	1.34
NH_4^+	$\frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4^-$	2.06	1.56	1.42
Na^+	NO_2^-	1.57	1.19	1.08

Table 4: Diffusion coefficients $\mathcal{D}/10^{-9}\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ for various salts

coefficient as well as rate constants. With the use of an activator the bacteria could compensate to some extent. Zhu [19] for example found that the effect of temperature on nitrification rates were not as significant as predicted by the van't Hoff-Arrhenius equation.

5. Conclusion

Pulse disturbances at very high ammonia concentrations of 7 mg/l $\text{NH}_3 - \text{N}$, at least for aquaculture and natural waters, yield zero order kinetics. As the concentrations fall to around 2 mg/l $\text{NH}_3 - \text{N}$ the kinetics pauses briefly before following half order or perhaps first order kinetics. Bicarbonate ions and phosphate ions are removed above stoichiometric requirements. The phosphate ions appear to be removed significantly faster after the switch to another phase. The high ammonia concentration disturbances required 13 hours before returning to typical pre pulse levels. Such a time interval does not preclude bacteria growth, but the quantities of bicarbonate ions and phosphates removed were higher than would be used by the bacteria for growth itself.

Pulse disturbances of around 0.7 mg/l $\text{NH}_3 - \text{N}$ reacted away in under 100 minutes. The first experiment showed a slow reaction rate that then became a very fast one. This type of curve is that seen from auto catalytic reactions. It suggests that the reaction rate is being very rapidly increased to take advantage of the ammonia pulse addition. A repeat experiment following 24 hours later yielded totally different kinetics more in line with zero order kinetics. The bacteria clearly can radically alter the reaction rate. It is suggested that this was done with the use of a low energy activator made during the very high ammonia pulse test. The bacteria would thus seem to use the activator based

upon the recent loading history. Subsequent pulse testing experiments were conducted after running for longer at the normal steady state conditions.

It was also determined that the pH fell to 4.0 with the buffering switched off. This pH coincides with the minimum at which bicarbonate ions are present in the bulk of the water.

The diffusion coefficient for ammonium carbonate salts is half of that of ammonia. The resulting liquid film transfer coefficient is then reduced by two thirds or more. This might explain in large part the need for a mass transfer correction factor in the previous paper.

The ammonia pulse kinetics suggests the use of activators as was suspected in the experimental aquaculture recycle data. The preliminary pulse kinetic experiments reveal findings to which no comprehensive explanation could be offered without the involvement of bicarbonate ions in combination with the use of phosphate ions as reactants, rather than as buffers. The results are thus compatible with a hypothesised carboxy pathway involved in ammonia oxidation. To investigate the nitrification reactions further and to obtain more information the main pulse tests were conducted.

Nomenclature

Symbols

C	Concentration of total ammonia nitrogen in bulk fluid	mg/l
$k_{I...II}$	Apparent rate equation constants (units depend upon equation)	
r	Rate of reaction	$mg/l/min$
R^2	Correlation coefficient	
T	Temperature	l/min
t	Time	min

Other Symbols

ω	Filter surface to water volume ratio	m^2/m^3
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Subscripts

in	Initial
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References

- [1] A. P. G. Newton, Evidence of carboxy ester mechanisms in nitrification from the dynamic reaction kinetics at natural concentrations. part 1 chi-square probability testing of common rate equations for the oxidation of

- ammonia in raw nitrification biofilters, in which the role of liquid film diffusion is accounted for, supports multiple molecule reaction mechanisms. (2023). doi:10.5281/Zenodo.8239188.
- [2] D. Van Krevelen, P. Hoftijzer, F. Huntjens, Composition and vapour pressures of aqueous solutions of ammonia, carbon dioxide and hydrogen sulphide, *Recueil des Travaux Chimiques des Pays-Bas* 68 (2) (1949) 191–216.
 - [3] F. Mani, M. Peruzzini, P. Stoppioni, CO₂ absorption by aqueous NH₃ solutions: speciation of ammonium carbamate, bicarbonate and carbonate by a ¹³C NMR study, *Green Chemistry* 8 (11) (2006) 995–1000.
 - [4] K. Kawazuishi, J. M. Prausnitz, Correlation of vapor-liquid equilibria for the system ammonia-carbon dioxide-water, *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research* 26 (7) (1987) 1482–1485.
 - [5] H. Holden, J. Thoden, F. Raushel, Carbamoyl phosphate synthetase: an amazing biochemical odyssey from substrate to product, *Cellular and Molecular Life Sciences CMLS* 56 (5) (1999) 507–522.
 - [6] F. Skinner, N. Walker, Growth of *Nitrosomonas europaea* in batch and continuous culture, *Archiv für Mikrobiologie* 38 (4) (1961) 339–349.
 - [7] A. B. Hooper, K. R. Terry, Specific inhibitors of ammonia oxidation in *Nitrosomonas*, *Journal of Bacteriology* 115 (2) (1973) 480–485.
 - [8] R. J. Olson, O. R. J., Differential photoinhibition of marine nitrifying bacteria: a possible mechanism for the formation of the primary nitrite maximum, *Journal of Marine Research* 39 (2) (1981) 227–238.
 - [9] S. Lu, X. Liu, C. Liu, G. Cheng, H. Shen, Influence of photoinhibition on nitrification by ammonia-oxidizing microorganisms in aquatic ecosystems, *Reviews in Environmental Science and Bio/Technology* (2020) 1–12.
 - [10] J. D. H. Strickland, T. R. Parsons, *A practical handbook of seawater analysis*, Fisheries research board of Canada, 1972.
 - [11] U. EPA, *Process design manual: Nitrogen control*. Washington, DC: US environmental protection agency. report nr 625, Tech. rep., R-93/010 (1993).
 - [12] J. Prehn, C. K. Waul, L.-F. Pedersen, E. Arvin, Impact of water boundary layer diffusion on the nitrification rate of submerged biofilter elements from a recirculating aquaculture system, *Water Research* 46 (11) (2012) 3516–3524.
 - [13] D. A. Wolf-Gladrow, R. E. Zeebe, C. Klaas, A. Körtzinger, A. G. Dickson, Total alkalinity: The explicit conservative expression and its application to biogeochemical processes, *Marine Chemistry* 106 (1-2) (2007) 287–300.
 - [14] H. Painter, A review of literature on inorganic nitrogen metabolism in microorganisms, *Water Research* 4 (6) (1970) 393–450.

- [15] D. Parkhurst, C. Appelo, Phreeqc (version 3)-a computer program for speciation, batch-reaction, one dimensional transport, and inverse geochemical calculations. usgs water res invest. report 99, Water Resources Investigations Report (1998) 99–4259.
- [16] R. Wilhelm, A. Abeliovich, A. Nejidat, Effect of long-term ammonia starvation on the oxidation of ammonia and hydroxylamine by nitrosomonas europaea, *The Journal of Biochemistry* 124 (4) (1998) 811–815.
- [17] V. N. Chowdiah, G. L. Foutch, G.-C. Lee, Binary liquid-phase mass transport in mixed-bed ion exchange at low solute concentration, *Industrial & engineering chemistry research* 42 (7) (2003) 1485–1494.
- [18] R. C. Reid, J. M. Prausnitz, B. E. Poling, *The properties of gases and liquids*, McGraw Hill Book Co., New York, NY, 1987.
- [19] S. Zhu, S. Chen, The impact of temperature on nitrification rate in fixed film biofilters, *Aquacultural Engineering* 26 (4) (2002) 221–237.